

VARIABILITY OF PERMEABILITY IN FIBRE PREFORMS MANUFACTURED WITH AUTOMATED FIBRE PLACEMENT (AFP)

Mikhail Y. Matveev¹, Andrew C. Long¹, I. Arthur Jones¹, Peter J. Schubel¹

¹Polymer Composites Research Group, Faculty of Engineering, The University of Nottingham, United Kingdom

Email: Mikhail.Matveev@nottingham.ac.uk

Keywords: Manufacturing, Permeability, Variability

ABSTRACT

Automated technologies for composite manufacturing such as Automated Fibre Placement (AFP) are on the list of the prospective solutions which can deliver both cost reduction and robust properties of the end product. Further improvements can be achieved by optimisation of resin infusion in RTM processing. However, it has been shown that this stage is likely to be affected by variability of permeability throughout a fibre preform. This variability can be potentially measured or predicted using models which can take into account variability in the fibre preform geometry. This paper describes a methodology for an automatic acquisition of internal geometry of the fibre preform. The data obtained from real preforms are then used to predict local permeability of the preforms.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite manufacturing with Automated Fibre Placement (AFP) or Automated Tape Lay-up (ATL) has already been employed by industry for several years. AFP/ATL helps to reduce costs of manufacturing by keeping waste of material minimal. A “dry fibre” AFP process (dry fibre tape on thermoplastic veil) followed by Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) provides a good alternative to a conventional AFP process which uses prepreg tapes despite the additional manufacturing step of resin infusion. A further cost reduction can be achieved by minimising defects and rejection rate which can occur during manufacturing (incomplete mould filling or incorrect temperature/cure cycle) using process design simulations. A conventional approach for process design is usually based on numerical simulation of coupled filling-curing problem using a single composite geometry with a nominal design (fibre volume fraction, fibre orientation, constant pressure etc). However, filling and curing of a real mould can be affected by variability of fibre preform geometry [1] and boundary conditions. This paper focuses on variability which stems from imprecision of tape lay-up and variability of source material (tape).

2 CHARACTERISATION OF AFP PREFORM

2.1 Specimen manufacturing

Two identical dry fibre AFP preforms were manufactured using a Coriolis AFP machine located in NCC UK and “dry fibre” yarns (24K carbon fibre tows, areal weight 194g/cm², width 6.35 mm) as source material. The machine was set to lay down straight tapes consisting of eight yarns 6.35mm (1/4”) wide each. A gap of 1mm between tapes was programmed to avoid possible overlaps of tapes. A simple cross-ply design of 16 layers (0°/90°)₈ was chosen for ease of manufacturing, characterisation and modelling. Layers had a regular shift of 3.5 yarn widths relative to a previous layer of the same direction. Thermoplastic binder on yarns was activated using a laser heating facility mounted on the lay-up head and yarns were compacted with 200N force applied via a soft roller. The laser power was set to 800W which gave surface temperature about 200°C at lay-up speed of 0.8 m/s and about 320°C at lay-up speed of 0.4 m/s. The first layer of each preform was laid down at a speed of 0.4 m/s, all other layers were laid down at 0.8m/s (except layers 2, 3, 4 in Panel 1 which were laid down at 0.6 m/s). Overall size of preforms was 1×1m which ensures that a part of the lay-up is free

from edge effects. An image of a preform with visible programmed gaps and defects (unintended gaps) is shown on Figure 1.

Figure 1: Programmed and unintended gaps in AFP preform

Several samples from Panel 1 were infused with Prime 20 LV resin using vacuum bagging technology, casted into polyester resin and then prepared for optical microscopy. Distinctive programmed gaps, small gaps between yarns within tapes and an unintended overlap can be seen on Figure 2 and Figure 3.

Figure 2: Typical cross-section in the 0° direction. Both programmed and non-programmed gaps are visible

Figure 3: An example of overlap between two yarns

2.2 Image acquisition and processing

A detailed image of each layer of both AFP preforms was acquired by pausing the AFP machine, mounting a 24MPix DSLR camera on a robotic arm and taking 84 images covering entire area of the preform with some overlaps. Resolution of images was about 35 μ m per pixel. The first image of each sequence included an image of a coordinate marker (fixed during all experiments) and calibration target. After images of a layer surface were acquired the AFP lay-up process was continued until the next layer was finished.

Raw camera images were processed using a range of MatLab tools. The processing algorithm for images of each layer was as follows:

1. Calibrate images in each layer into a plane parallel to the tool surface using the calibration target and assign scale to each layer (can have small variations from layer to layer due to remounting of the camera)
2. Calculate exact image overlaps i.e. relative shifts (in principle this step can be used to create a mosaic image of an entire layer but it is impractical due to the size of such an image which is 24 \times 84 MPix)
3. Perform image detection on each image separately
4. Combine detected edges of yarns together using information from Step 2
5. Transform positions of detected edges into a global coordinate system using information about the coordinate marker position in the layer
6. Repeat for the next layer

One of the main challenges of the processing was to have a good contrast between adjacent yarns and yarns belonging to different layers. This can be achieved by placing a powerful light source perpendicular to the fibre direction which results in brighter colours for a previous layer of yarns parallel to the light source. However, binder veil, which is used for yarn coating, reflects light in all the directions and hence yarns blend together on the images. This prevents precise edge detection between yarns touching each other (see Figure 4). Since yarns positions are approximately known, detection of unintended gaps between yarns within a tape is still possible.

Figure 4: Example of poor contrast between two adjacent yarns

Error of the edge detection algorithm was estimated by comparing edges detected in the overlapping area of two neighbouring images. It was found that error tend to be normally distributed

with mean of 1.2 pixels and standard deviation of 1.76 pixels for both of the manufactured panels. A non-zero mean of the error is probably related to dissimilar lighting in the neighbouring images.

2.3 Statistical analysis of AFP lay-up

Information about detected yarn edges makes it possible to create a very precise model of an actual lay-up. However, this seems to be impractical for industrial application since the procedure of taking images is time consuming and a detailed model cannot be run for every manufactured panel (at least not a high fidelity model). Alternatively, lay-up can be described in a statistical way which then can be used to create a statistical model of a preform for further simulation. Since the focus of the paper is on the permeability of preforms the main statistical descriptors should describe gaps between tapes and yarns i.e. distribution of gap variation between two tapes which is shown in Figure 5. The mean of the gap width was found to be 0.75 mm and its standard deviation was 0.15 mm.

Figure 5: Distribution of programmed gap width in AFP preform

Other statistical descriptors such as correlation length, variation between preforms and between layers were found to have no obvious trend and hence are not presented here.

3 PERMEABILITY MODEL

The heterogeneity and complex geometry of fibre preforms make it difficult to create a model which could include all the levels of interaction. A conventional approach to permeability modelling is based on a multi-scale paradigm which suggests progressive homogenisation of properties through the scales starting from the micro-scale (fibre bundles) to the meso-scale (several yarns) and the macro-scale (a part). A heterogeneous medium of one scale is substituted with a homogeneous medium with the same equivalent properties at a higher scale. In this case the geometry of the AFP preform at the meso-scale should be viewed as a layered structure with layer consisting of homogeneous tapes with gaps between them as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Example of poor contrast between two adjacent yarns

Permeability at each of the scale can be described by a 2nd rank tensor which can be written as a symmetric 3×3 matrix:

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{pmatrix} K_{xx} & K_{xy} & K_{xz} \\ & K_{yy} & K_{yz} \\ \text{symm.} & & K_{zz} \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where x and y are direction in plane of fibre orientations and z is perpendicular to that plane.

At the meso-scale it can be assumed that off-diagonal z -components of tensor (1) are negligible compared with other components due to the absence of diagonal flow between top and bottom surface. This assumption makes it possible to treat problems of finding in-plane, \mathbf{K}_{in} , and out-of-plane, $K_{through}$, (through-thickness) permeabilities separately. In-plane permeability, \mathbf{K}_{in} , in this case can be represented as 2×2 matrix:

$$\mathbf{K}_{in} = \begin{pmatrix} K_{xx} & K_{xy} \\ K_{xy} & K_{yy} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

3.1 In-plane permeability

Starting from the scale of fibres, fibre bundle (yarns) are homogenised using Gebart formulae [2] for permeability of yarns in direction along, $K_{y,\parallel}$, and transverse to fibres, $K_{y,\perp}$.

$$K_{y,\parallel} = \frac{8R^2 (1 - V_f)^3}{53 V_f^2} \quad (3)$$

$$K_{y,\perp} = \frac{16}{9\pi} \sqrt{\frac{1}{6} \left(\frac{V_{f,max}}{V_f} - 1 \right)^{2.5}} \quad (4)$$

where R is the fibre radius, V_f is the fibre volume fraction and $V_{f,max}$ is the maximum fibre volume fraction in hexagonal packing.

Permeability of a single layer along fibres can be calculated using weighted averaging approach [3] assuming parallel flow in the gaps and yarns:

$$K_{l,\parallel} = \phi K_g + (1 - \phi) K_{y,\parallel} \quad (5)$$

where ϕ is the ratio of volume of gaps to overall volume of the layer, K_g is permeability of a gap calculated using Poiseuille's law:

$$K_g = \frac{b^2}{12} \left(1 - \frac{192b}{\pi^5 a} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\tanh\left(\frac{(2i-1)\pi a}{2b}\right)}{(2i-1)^5} \right) \quad (6)$$

where a and b are dimension of the gap, N is the number of terms in the series (10 was found to be sufficient in this paper).

Assuming flow across the gaps has negligible contribution to the overall flow, the weighted averaging approach can be used to calculate permeability of a single layer across fibres:

$$\frac{1}{K_{l,\perp}} \approx \frac{(1 - \phi)}{K_{y,\perp}} \quad (7)$$

The permeability tensor of a layer, \mathbf{K}_i , can be written as:

$$\mathbf{K}_i = \begin{pmatrix} K_{l,\parallel} & 0 \\ 0 & K_{l,\perp} \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Flow in a multi-layer preform is represented as series of flow connected in series and/or parallel depending on geometry and flow direction. The overall in-plane permeability of the preform can be found using equation:

$$\mathbf{K}_{in} = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{t_i}{T} \mathbf{R}(\alpha_i) \cdot \mathbf{K}_i \cdot \mathbf{R}(\alpha_i) \quad (9)$$

where t_i is the thickness of i -th layer, T is the overall thickness, \mathbf{R} is rotation matrix and α_i is the orientation of i -th layer in a chosen reference coordinate system.

3.2 Through-thickness permeability

The in-plane permeability was computed assuming that flows in adjacent layer do not interact with each other i.e. there is no fluid exchange between layers. In contrast, through-thickness permeability directly depends on how flow in the adjacent layers interacts.

It is proposed to separate a preform into a number of inter-layers which include half of two adjacent layers. So the number of inter-layers is equal to the number of layers and each of them contains features from two adjacent layers. Assuming ideal periodicity of the structure, each trans-layer is then dissected into simple channels where flow assumed to be laminar and parallel to the channel direction. Boundaries of the channels are assumed to be non-permeable and act as no-slip walls. The scheme of trans-layer division into channel is shown in Figure 7. The model represents a simplified unit cell with ideal symmetry boundary conditions applied to its edges. Flow in such a model can be considered as a flow entering a gap from a previous inter-layer cell and the flowing through the system of channels as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Through-thickness flow model

The electric-hydraulic analogy can be used to represent the problem as well. In this case, it becomes straightforward to compute overall hydraulic resistance, R^* , of the system:

$$R_g = R + \tilde{R} + R' + \frac{R_1 R_2}{R_1 + R_2} + \frac{R'_1 R'_2}{R'_1 + R'_2} \quad (10)$$

where $R, R', \tilde{R}, R_1, R_2, R'_1, R'_2$ are hydraulic resistances of channels and part of channels shown in Figure 11 which can be calculated from permeabilities of gaps, K , as:

$$R = \frac{\mu L}{AK} \quad (11)$$

where μ is viscosity of a fluid, L is the length of a channel, A is the area of gap cross-section.

3.3 Numerical validation of the models

The proposed model was validated using finite element analysis performed in ANSYS CFX using a model of four orthogonal gaps (i.e. four-layer preform) shown in Figure 8. The analytical in-plane model yielded results within 10% of the numerical model for all the considered cases (see Figure 9). For the through-thickness model, it was found that the proposed model yields a good comparison with the numerical model in case of low porosities and low layer thickness as can be seen in Figure 10.

Figure 8: Model of four orthogonal gaps

Figure 9: Comparison of theoretical and numerical predictions of in-plane permeability of a four-layer orthogonal preform

Figure 10: Comparison of theoretical and numerical predictions of through-thickness permeability of a four-layer orthogonal preform

The poor agreement between theoretical and numerical prediction of through-thickness permeability for large porosities and large thicknesses is explained by a simplification of flow between intersecting channels. It was assumed that the flow makes “perpendicular turn” while in reality it will find a shorter around a corner. This simplification has lower impact on the models with larger distance between channel intersections and thinner layer.

4 VARIABILITY MODELLING

The model described in the previous section can be used to predict permeability of the reinforcement as designed (expected permeability). The same model can be employed to estimate local permeabilities in a real reinforcement using experimental data about geometry of the reinforcement. Local variations in permeability can be calculated for an element of material which has a characteristic length of eight yarns and a gap (~ 52 mm). At this scale, the measured width of programmed gap (from first two layers only) was used to compute local permeability. Results of the calculations and experimental results for a preform with overall porosity of 0.41 are presented in Table 1. A map of local in-plane permeability within one layer of the preform is presented as an example in Figure 11.

Permeability		Nominal (as designed)	Predicted with variability	Experimental
K_{xx}	$[10^{-11} \text{ m}^2]$	2.91	2.74 ± 0.24	2.51 ± 0.18
K_{zz}	$[10^{-13} \text{ m}^2]$	3.41	3.27 ± 0.15	-

Table 1: Measured and predicted permeabilities of AFP preforms (overall porosity = 0.41)

Figure 11: Map of in-plane permeability (K_{xx}) variations within one layer

In-plane permeability calculated with use of realistic geometry is about 5% lower than that predicted with the use of the nominal design geometry. At the same time it is 9% larger than experimentally measured permeability. The through-thickness permeability of the preform with the nominal design was also found to be higher than permeability of a preform with variability in geometry. Map of local in-plane permeability shows

9 CONCLUSIONS

The algorithm developed and employed for analysis of internal geometry of AFP preforms was shown to be helpful in estimation of variability of AFP process. It was found that the gap between tapes, which provides the main path for flow in preform, is lower than the nominal programmed gap and has variation of up to 20%. The future work on geometry characterisation should include study of the correlation of the gap width within tapes, between layers and between preforms.

Closed form solution models for in-plane and through thickness permeability were presented and employed for prediction of the local permeability. It was found that permeability of a preform with variability is lower than that of a nominal design. Coefficient of variation of permeability was found to be below 10%.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Authors acknowledge financial support of EPSRC through research grant “Robustness and performance of automated composite manufacturing”. NCC, UK staff are gratefully acknowledged for their help with the AFP process. They also acknowledge useful discussions on the design of the experiments with colleagues in the School of Mathematical Sciences, University of Nottingham.

REFERENCES

1. Endruweit, A. and A.C. Long, *Influence of stochastic variations in the fibre spacing on the permeability of bi-directional textile fabrics*. Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2006. **37**(5): p. 679-694.
2. Gebart, B.R., *Permeability of Unidirectional Reinforcements for Rtm*. Journal of Composite Materials, 1992. **26**(8): p. 1100-1133.
3. Endruweit, A. and A.C. Long, *A model for the in-plane permeability of triaxially braided reinforcements*. Composites Part A-Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2011. **42**(2): p. 165-172.